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D3.3 - Holistic Interoperability Toolkit V1

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Abbreviations

ARC	AMEAS Research Center
DL	Deep Learning
EC	European Commission
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
H2020	Horizon 2020 Program of the European Commission
HVAC	Heating, Ventilation and Air Conditioning
IoT	Internet of Things
IUDX	Indian Urban Data Exchange
kNN	k-Nearest Neighbour
ML	Machine Learning
NexIOM	NASA Exploration Initiatives Ontology Models
OASC	Open & Agile Smart Cities
QUDT	Quantities, Units, Dimensions and Types
SAREF	Smart Applications Reference
SOSA	Sensor, Observation, Sample and Actuator
SSN	Semantic Sensor Network
VPME	Virtualized Policy Management Environment
WP	Work Package

Executive summary

Data can be represented in a variety of ways. It's structure usually only takes into consideration the local context for what that data will be used for. As such, different data structures present a challenge for accessing and reusing data for other purposes other than originally planned and especially for combining data from different sources. This hurdle assumes yet another when considering the differences in the semantic description the information represented using different Data Models.

Thus, following task T3.2 - Ontologies and Archetypes for Semantic Interoperability, this deliverable presents the developed prototype solution for a “...*holistic interoperability toolkit ... that will provide standard means or foundation principles by which data may be described, categorized, and shared, considering its data description, data context, data linking, reusability and sharing.*”.

This deliverable outlines a solution based on supporting a collection of Data Models which allow for the representation of the data in any of the supported models. The models are imported into a generic structure understood by the catalogue consisting of four hierarchical levels. These are a Data Model level containing a name, description and source of the model, a data concept level describing the entity to which the data refers to i.e., weather data or traffic data for instance. A Measurable level containing the properties which describe the entity such as temperature, traffic volume or specific state and a Unit level containing information about how that measurable is presented. This semantic relations between different Data Models are mapped through the developed matchmaking solution that combines semantic vector search and human decision. Thanks to this mapping, the search engine (also a part of the Interoperability Toolkit) is able to explore the supporting collection of Data Models and locate equivalent representations of data. Together, they enable the representation of data in different formats which in turn makes it possible to join and interpret data from various heterogenous sources in a desired output model.

This deliverable is one of two related to the developed of the Interoperability Toolkit. The next one will focus on improving and applying the prototype on the datasets collected from the AI4PublicPolicy pilots and on the handling of policies.

1 Introduction

1.1 The AI4PublicPolicy Project

AI4PublicPolicy is a joint effort of policy makers and Cloud/AI experts to unveil AI’s potential for automated, transparent and citizen-centric development of public policies. To this end, the project will deliver, validate, demonstrate and promote a novel Open Cloud platform (i.e., AI4PublicPolicy platform) for automated, scalable, transparent and citizen-centric policy management based on unique AI technologies.

The AI4PublicPolicy platform will be an Open Virtualized Policy Management Environment (VPME) that will provide fully-fledged policy development/management functionalities based on AI technologies such as Machine Learning (ML), Deep Learning (DL), NLP and chatbots, while leveraging citizens’ participation and feedback. It will support the entire policy development lifecycle, based on technologies for the extraction, simulation, evaluation and optimization of interoperable and reusable public policies, with emphasis on citizen-centric policies development and optimization through the realization of citizen-oriented feedback loops. AI4PublicPolicy will complement public policy development functionalities with the ever-important process reengineering and organization transformation activities towards ensuring the effective transition from legacy policy development models to emerging AI-based policy making.

The AI4PublicPolicy VPME will be integrated with EOSC with a dual objective. First to facilitate access to the Cloud and HPC resources of EOSC/EGI that are required to enable the project’s AI tools, second to boost the sustainability and wider use of the project’s developments. AI4PublicPolicy’s business plan for sustaining, expanding, and commercializing the AI tools and the VPME is based on the development of a community of interested and engaged stakeholders (i.e., public authorities and other policy makers) around the project’s platform.

Figure 1. AI4PublicPolicy methodological approach

1.2 Objective of the Deliverable

This deliverable is related to task T3.2 - Ontologies and Archetypes for Semantic Interoperability, where its entire objective is described, namely *"incorporate mechanisms for adaptive selection of assets (terms, datasets and policies), correction and/or removal of inaccurate data. Hence, a holistic interoperability toolkit will be introduced that will provide standard means or foundation principles by which data may be described, categorized, and shared, considering its data description, data context, data linking, reusability and sharing."* The main objective of this deliverable is to present prototypes of the technologies of the Semantic Interoperability Toolkit that allow to discover and collect datasets regardless of the semantic models used to describe them.

1.3 Structure of the Deliverable

This document is comprised of the following Sections:

- Section 2 – Interoperability Toolkit Overview: Introduces the goals for the Semantic Interoperability Toolkit and contextualizes it within the Ai4PublicPolicy project.
- Section 3 – Data Models: Provides an introduction to the concept of Data Models and their uses, as well as an overview of the structure developed for the Data Model Catalogue.
- Section 4 – Matchmaking Solution: This chapter describes the prototype for identifying and establishing semantic mappings between concepts of different data models.
- Section 5 – Semantic Data Queries: This chapter describes the prototype for implementing semantic queries.
- Section 6 – Validation Models: Contains a description of the different Data Models used for the validation of Semantic Interoperability Toolkit.
- Section 7 – Conclusion and Future Work: Final thoughts on the developed toolkit and a discussion on future work.

2 Interoperability Toolkit Overview

The Interoperability toolkit aims at providing a collection of tools and resources that support the execution of data discovery and manipulation over different semantically described information. These tools can be classified in the following classes:

- **Mapping of Semantic Concepts:** This class refers to the tools used to identify relations between semantic concepts defined in different Data Models. This mapping allows to establish relations between different Data Models, describing how datasets conforming to different Data Modes can be related and converted.
- **Data Indexing and Collection:** Refers to tools that support the discover and indexing of data sets that satisfy any query specification, regardless of the Data Model used to describe the datasets. It also refers to tools used to interact with data sources for purpose of collect the relevant information.

Figure 2 represents how the Semantic Interoperability Toolkit interacts with other components of AI4PublicPolicy. The Semantic Interoperability Toolkit integrates into the Catalogue of Datasets and Policies to provide capabilities to handle information described using disparate semantic definitions. With these capabilities Policy Makers can use the Catalogue to discover and inspect Datasets and Policies regardless of the semantic descriptions associated to each dataset or policy. After the Policy Maker identifies the Policies and/or Datasets that are of interest to him, we can export them to the Data Management component under the semantic description and format more suitable for the AI Models used on the VPME.

Figure 2. Overview of role of Semantic Interoperability Toolkit

3 Data Models

In the same way that concepts can be described in a variety of different ways, through different words or descriptions, so too can data. This presents a challenge for interpreting and reusing data, particularly across domains, since the decided upon structure hinges on domain needs. Accessing someone's data requires knowing its structure, which if different every time, requires learning it every time. This chapter presents a solution to create a catalogue of data models that will support the search and semantic analysis between the Semantic Concepts of different models. This section presents a brief overview about the Data Models and the major concepts associated to them and presents the approach to model the major concepts of data models in a Catalogue of Data Models.

Data models are a visual representation of either a whole information system or a part of the whole, by using standardized schemas. These models serve to illustrate types of data, the relationships between data, how it is structured, in what format and what are its attributes and properties. In essence, a data model looks to make data meaningful and data communication possible based on three concepts [1] [2]:

1. A set of data structures outlining operations and constraints. They encompass the description of data types, properties, and descriptions.
2. A set of operators and inference rules describing the methods and types that the data model employs.
3. A set of constraints describing syntax, dependencies and constraints that ensure the model's accuracy, validity, and compatibility.

Furthermore, a data model consists of three levels [3] [4]:

1. A conceptual level for communicating ideas to users about the domain and defining entities and relationships.
2. A logical level, also referred to as a schema, for communicating ideas to designers about domain applications.
3. A physical level which refers to the actual physical storage and implementation in a database management system.

Models tend to be domain specific as they are constructed to serve specific needs. In an initial stage the relevant stakeholders should formulate the requirements that the system should address. These requirements are then translated into the specific data structure of model. Usually, this structure is not immutable. As requirements change over time, so too should the data model adapt to these changes and due to this, the data model should try to maintain a certain level of abstraction to ensure this flexibility (although varying degrees of abstraction can be employed depending on the needs).

This abstraction also makes it possible to reuse or adapt existing schemas to other contexts which is one the benefits of their use. The other one is that, by using these standardized schemas,

interoperability of data can be achieved, because everyone is describing the same thing in the same way. Otherwise, it may become difficult, or outright impossible, to make sense or extract information from data where it is not known how it is structured.

3.1 Data Model Representation

To support the representation of several data models in a single space, this space needs to support a generic enough representation that allows for expressing all the semantic concepts of each Data Model and put them on a common base that supports the comparison of semantic meanings. Therefore, it was implemented as four concepts in a hierarchical model in the web framework to support the representation to the different data models:

- **Data Model:** This concept represents the root to each Data Model. It identifies the name of the Data Model and a description. This concept allows it to be associated with multiple child Data Models to support the representation of the several levels of data models (some data models may be divided in multiple Data Models to simplify the internal organisation). A Data Model can also be linked to multiple Data Concepts.

A Data Model is described with the following interface:

```

1 interface DataModel {
2     schemaId:string,
3     name:string,
4     description:string,
5     isParentOf?:string[],
6     website?:string,
7     githubRepository?:string,
8     metadata?:Metadata
9 }

```

Figure 3. Representation of a Data Model in Typescript

- **Data Concept:** A Data Concept corresponds to an application domain for an aggregation of data, where the different data measurements and properties are used together to better describe the state of something. Similarly, to the Data Models, Data Concepts can also be children of other Data Concepts when needed to represent application domains that are specification/derivations of domains. A Data Concept can be represented by multiple Measurable Quantities.

A Data Concept is described by the following interface:

```

1 interface DataConcept {
2     name:string,
3     description: string,
4     dataSetMeasurableQuantities:DataSetMeasurableQuantity[],
5     images?:ElementImage[],
6     schemaId:string,
7     isParentOf?:string[],
8     metadata?:Metadata
9 }

```

Figure 4. Representation of a Data Concept in Typescript

- **Measurable Quantity:** Measurable Quantities represent anything that can be measurable, quantified or specific information distributed under different formats, such as images or text. Measurable Quantities may represent a property of something (e.g., mass, length, temperature, etc.), the count of an amount (just to represent some cases) or a property of a concept they are related to. For instance, when describing traffic volume in a particular model instead of quantifying it, it may be described by an enumerated variable such as low, medium, and high volumes of traffic, a property 'type' would be another example. Measurable quantities may represent a large spectrum of properties, ranging from static properties,

passing through properties that change with time or geographic location, to responses to a questionnaire. Values of Measurable Quantities may be represented in different units or be dimensionless/unitless.

A Measurable Quantity is described by the following interface:

```

1  interface MeasurableQuantity {
2      name: string,
3      description: string,
4      unitIds: string[],
5      schemaId: string,
6      isParentOf?:string[],
7      metadata?:Metadata
8  }

```

Figure 5. Representation of a Measurable Quantity in Typescript

- **Unit:** A Unit represents the magnitude of a specific Measurement Quantity according to a given system of units.

A Unit is described by the following interface:

```

1  interface Unit {
2      name: string,
3      symbol:string,
4      lastUpdate?: Date,
5      status?: string[],
6      schemaId: string,
7      metadata?:Metadata
8  }

```

Figure 6. Representation of a Unit in Typescript

3.1.1 Mapping example

By accessing the GitHub repositories for the different models, the corresponding JSON or Turtle¹ (.ttl) files that describe their structure and composition are parsed and transformed into a data model, data concept, measurable and unit hierarchy.

Figure 7 shows an entry for a QUDT quantitykind (which will be transformed into measurable quantity for the framework as in Figure 8). The fields of interest such as the label, description, and informative links are parsed and used to generate the new object by using the script shown in Figure 9. It can also be seen that a `qudt:applicableUnit` field exists. Using this field, it is possible to establish the connection between the `qudt:quantitykind` and the unit. Taking into account Figure 5 the `quantitykind:Absorbance` is transformed into a `MeasurableQuantity` as follows:

- `rdfs:label` ⇒ `name`
- `qudt:plainTextDescription` ⇒ `description`
- `qudt:applicableUnit` ⇒ `unitIds`
- `qudt:informativeReference` ⇒ `metadata`

¹ [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Turtle_\(syntax\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Turtle_(syntax))

```

quantitykind:Absorptance
  a qudt:QuantityKind ;
  qudt:applicableUnit unit:UNITLESS ;
  qudt:hasDimensionVector qkv:A0E0L0I0M0H0T0D1 ;
  qudt:informativeReference "http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Absorptance"^^xsd:anyURI ;
  qudt:informativeReference "https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Absorptance"^^xsd:anyURI ;
  qudt:informativeReference "https://www.researchgate.net/post/Absorptance_or_absorbance"^^xsd:anyURI ;
  qudt:latexDefinition "\\(\\alpha = \\frac{\\Phi_a}{\\Phi_m}\\), where \\(\\Phi_a\\) is the absorbed radiant flux or the absorbed luminous flux, and \\(\\Phi_m\\) is the radiant flux or luminous flux of the incident radiation."^^qudt:LaTeXString ;
  qudt:latexSymbol "\\(\\alpha\\)"^^qudt:LaTeXString ;
  qudt:plainTextDescription "Absorptance is the ratio of the radiation absorbed by a surface to that incident upon it. Also known as absorbance." ;
  qudt:systemDerivedQuantityKind qudt:500_SI ;
  vae:todo "belongs to 500-ISO" ;
  rdfs:isDefinedBy <http://qudt.org/2.1/vocab/quantitykind> ;
  rdfs:label "Absorptance"@en ;
  .
    
```

Figure 7. QUDT quantitykind

Figure 8. Unparallel’s web framework concepts, units and measurements

```

keys = Object.keys(object);
if(keys.includes('@type')){
  if(object['@type'] === 'qudt:QuantityKind'){
    id = object['@id'];
    name = rdfsLabelNone(keys, object);
    if(keys.includes('qudt:plainTextDescription')){ //['qudt:plainTextDescription']
      description = object['qudt:plainTextDescription'];
    }
    else if(keys.includes('dcterms:description')){
      if(object['dcterms:description'].hasOwnProperty('value')){
        description = object['dcterms:description']['value'];
        description = clean_description(description);
      }
      else{
        description = object['dcterms:description'];
      }
      description = clean_description(description);
    }
    measurable = newMeasurable(clean_name(name), id, description);
    if(keys.includes('qudt:dbpediaMatch')){
      measurable.references.push(newRef(object['qudt:dbpediaMatch']['value']));
    }
    if(keys.includes('qudt:informativeReference')){
      if(Array.isArray(object['qudt:informativeReference'])){
        measurable.references.push(newRef(object['qudt:informativeReference']['value']));
      }
      else{
        for(let ref of object['qudt:informativeReference']){
          measurable.references.push(newRef(ref['value']));
        }
      }
    }
  }
  if(object.hasOwnProperty('qudt:applicableUnit')){
    if(Array.isArray(object['qudt:applicableUnit'])){
      for(let pref of prefixes){
        if(object['qudt:applicableUnit']['@id'].includes(pref)){
          isMultiplier = true;
          measurableId = object['qudt:applicableUnit']['@id'].replaceAll(pref, '');
        }
      }
    }
  }
}
    
```

Figure 9. Creation of a measurable from a QUDT quantitykind

The different data models are imported to the model in the web framework, creating a collection of data models that can then be used to allow for different representations of the same data. The idea

is to allow the mapping of semantic concepts of different data models with the help of the developed matchmaking solution.

4 Semantic Matchmaking

This chapter aims at describing the adopted approach for making queries to the database where the content of several Data Models is stored. The success of this task determines the capability of the matchmaking solution to efficiently retrieve similar content, regardless of it being structured differently in each Data Model. This means that it is expected that the algorithm can, for instance, identify different units of temperature across the several Data Models while being able to unify duplicate units despite their distinct symbols or representations.

4.1 Approach

When it comes to search algorithms, vector search emerges as one of the most promising technologies supported by four major motivations:

- Semantic – users increasingly expect search engines to deliver results according to the meaning of their input, rather than comparing the words or characters themselves. This stands as a great challenge because people often find different ways to ask for the same thing.
- Input flexibility – it is sometimes preferable to provide the input in alternative formats other than text (e.g., images or even speech).
- Context and domain specificity – users expect relevance to be tightly coupled with the subject at hand, or with the context where a context is issued.
- Precise and unique – the search results should be as accurate as possible. The less time it takes to find what the user is looking for the better.

To achieve its results, vector search relies on vector similarity which essentially consists of encoding both the universe of results and the user input using the same Machine Learning model (usually a Deep Learning Neural Network) and then returning the results with the highest score (i.e., similarity), as represented in Figure 10 [5].

Figure 10. Vector search overview

If we take a closer look at the image above, it becomes clear that a preparation stage is required before being able to make queries.

Firstly, it is essential to ensure that each piece of data contains the vectorial representation, also known as embedding, of the field(s) that will be used for searching purposes. For that, a Machine Learning model is required. It goes without saying that identifying the context of the data to be searched is essential, as it influences the choice of the model, the quality of the embeddings and, consequently, the accuracy of the results.

Once the model is selected, it is fed with the values of the fields we want to be searchable and returns a mathematical representation for each one, i.e., a dense vector. Depending on the model, the generated vectors can have different dimensions (i.e., positions). The higher the vector's dimensionality, the more precise will be the results because there is more information to compare against. On the other hand, more dimensions require more computational resources and lead to increased processing time.

Finally, the data is inserted into the database along with the corresponding embeddings for the desired fields. Only after this setup is the infrastructure ready to deliver meaningful results.

Similarly, when it comes to making queries, the search input provided by the user is run through the same Machine Learning model. As soon as the embedding of the search query is available, it is possible to compute the similarity with each of the embeddings stored in the database during the preparation stage. This calculation can be carried out through different mathematical formulas, which are often based on one of the following vectorial operations:

- L^2 distance, also known as Euclidean distance, which for two vectors $a, b \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is given by

$$d_{L^2}(a, b) = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (a_i - b_i)^2}$$

- Dot product which, for two vectors $a, b \in \mathbb{R}^n$, equals

$$\vec{a} \cdot \vec{b} = \sum_{i=1}^n a_i b_i$$

- Cosine of the angle, θ , between the two vectors, $a, b \in \mathbb{R}^n$, which can be calculated by

$$\cos(\theta) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n a_i b_i}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n a_i^2} \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n b_i^2}}$$

These vectorial operations are used to create a compound formula that outputs the so-called score for each possible result. Finally, a k-Nearest Neighbours algorithm is applied to find the k results with the highest score. For that, the results are sorted by their score in descending order and the k-first ones are returned.

The described approach is expected to deliver accurate matches for our use case because, as it relies on vectorial representations of the data, the algorithm can find semantically equivalent sentences, i.e., similarities beyond the words themselves or the characters that form them.

4.2 Implementation

Each phase of the approach can be put into practice by resorting to a range of tools and frameworks. This subsection describes the adopted technologies and the way they were put to work together towards the goal of finding similar concepts across multiple Data Models, each with its structure and terminology.

The interactions between the main components are summarised below.

Figure 11. Matchmaking solution overview

As represented in Figure 11, an external service is responsible for generating the embeddings of the data, stored in a MongoDB instance, that we want to be searchable. This database is continuously synchronized with an Elasticsearch instance which is then used by the Unparallel Innovation's web framework to retrieve the results of the user's queries.

4.2.1 External Service

The infrastructure where the Data Models to be searched are stored is the Unparallel Innovation's web framework. Its capabilities can be expanded by external applications through the External Service library, whose communication is powered through the following queueing and a data subscription system.

4.2.1.1 Connection and authentication

The application uses the external service to establish a connection with the web framework by sending an authentication token and a JSON describing what the application can do. When received, the request is processed and, if a service is found, it is assigned to the application.

4.2.1.2 Queue and data subscription

A queue subscription is made when an external service is assigned and allows the application to receive actions from the web framework, process them and reply with a JSON response. The result is then processed using the appropriate methods related with the type of the external service.

A subscription also allows the user to have access to data stored on the framework that is authorized to the user, including live updates each time a data element is added, changed, or deleted.

4.2.1.3 Flow overview

The following diagram gives an overview of the connection, authentication and subscription flow between the External Service library and the Unparallel Innovation's web framework.

Figure 12. External Service flow overview

As described before, the text embedding of the field(s) is what makes the information searchable. Therefore, it was necessary to find a way of obtaining the dense vectors of any desired Data Model’s field.

Considering that the web framework is developed in JavaScript, an external service that uses a node.js library for computing the embeddings turned out to be the best way to implement this step of the flow. Since TensorFlow is a widely accepted open-source library for Machine Learning tasks, its Universal Sentence Encoder² was the chosen model to generate the 512-dimensional vectors of text embeddings, given a sentence or group of sentences as input. The field whose embeddings were obtained and considered was the *name* of the Data Concepts, Data Models, Measurable Quantities and Units.

4.2.2 Elasticsearch

Once the embeddings are all stored in the database, the infrastructure is ready to receive search queries. For this, a search-powered engine is required. Due to its ability to handle searches within large amounts of data and the native support for k-Nearest-Neighbour-based search, Elasticsearch³ was the selected option.

Since the web framework uses a MongoDB instance to store the Data Models and the embeddings, a syncing tool is also necessary. The Monstache syncing daemon was used for this. However, for

² <https://www.npmjs.com/package/@tensorflow-models/universal-sentence-encoder>

³ <https://www.elastic.co>

the *knn* search option from Elasticsearch to work, the fields where the text embeddings are stored need to be converted from the default type *float* to *dense_vector*. Hence, for each search index, a mapping must be generated with a PUT request to */collection.new_index*, which becomes associated with a new empty search index. The request body represented in Figure 13 only contains the definition of the embedding field, for illustrative purposes. To be exact, all the other fields must be described in the body as well. Notice that this is where the similarity function is also selected.

```
{
  "mappings": {
    "properties": {
      "_embedding.name": {
        "type": "dense_vector",
        "dims": 512,
        "index": true,
        "similarity": "<similarity_function>" // l2_norm, dot_product_or_cosine
      }
    }
  }
}
```

Figure 13. Request body to create a mapping

Afterwards, it is necessary to populate the new index by reindexing the data according to the mapping that has just been provided. This is done with a POST request to */reindex*, with the body shown in Figure 14.

```
{
  "source": {
    "index": "<collection.index>"
  },
  "dest": {
    "index": "<collection.new_index>"
  }
}
```

Figure 14. Request body for reindexing

Finally, Elasticsearch can be used to retrieve search results through a POST request to */collection.new_index/_search* with the body portrayed in Figure 15.

```
{
  "knn": {
    "field": "name",
    "query_vector": "<embeddings_array>",
    "k": "<k>",
    "num_candidates": "<num_candidates>"
  },
  "fields": "<fields_to_receive>",
  "_source": "<fields_to_receive_from_source>",
  "size": "<max_response_elements>"
}
```

Figure 15. Search query body

As shown above, the following input is provided to the query:

- *field* – the name of the field that contains the embeddings
- *query_vector* – the array of embeddings
- *k* – the number of nearest neighbours
- *num_candidates* – the number of candidates to consider, since the *knn* option runs an approximate kNN search
- *fields* – the fields to receive in the reply
- *_source* – the fields from the source to include in the reply

- *size* – the maximum number of elements included in the response

4.2.3 Demonstrator

Using the described technique, it was possible to implement a visual representation of the comparison between all pieces of data of a certain entity (e.g., Data Concept, Data Model, Measurable Quantity, Unit).

Algorithm type: Euclidean distance Number of results: 10 K: 2000 Number of candidates: 2000			
Name	Higher score	Average score	Score
e.g. Thermometer or *meter	e.g. 10 or >10 or <10 or =10	e.g. Thermometer or *meter	e.g. Thermometer or *meter
Year	100%	62%	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Score: 100% Name:Year Score: 68% Name:Common Year Score: 58% Name:Sideral Year Score: 57% Name:Time in days Score: 56% Name:Number per Year Score: 56% Name:Month Score: 56% Name:Reciprocal Year Score: 55% Name:Weeks Score: 55% Name:Per Second Score: 55% Name:Number per year
Watt	100%	66%	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Score: 100% Name:Watt Score: 73% Name:Watts Score: 71% Name:Watt Ton Score: 66% Name:Watt Second Score: 61% Name:Watthour Score: 61% Name:Watts Per Liter Score: 57% Name:Watt Hour Score: 57% Name:Watts Per Meter Score: 56% Name:Watts Per Inch Score: 56% Name:Kelvin Meter Per Watt
Volt Ampere Reactive Hour	100%	78%	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Score: 100% Name:Volt Ampere Reactive Hour Score: 86% Name:Volt Ampere Hour Score: 86% Name:Volt Ampere Hour Score: 84% Name:Volt Ampere Reactive Score: 77% Name:Volts Ampere Reactive Score: 73% Name:Volt Ampere Score: 73% Name:Volt Ampere Score: 71% Name:Voltampere Reactive Hours Score: 69% Name:Volts Per Hours Score: 66% Name:Volts Per Minutes

Figure 16. Matchmaking results for Units

Figure 16 shows, for some entries of the Units entity, the highest scoring results (e.g., there is a unit called Year in two of the Data Models; there is a Watt unit in two of the Data Models and another one called Watts – 73% similar – in a different model). These results were obtained through the kNN algorithm using the Euclidean distance as the similarity function. The dot product and cosine similarity functions, along with other parameters for the queries are also available on the top. Additionally, the results in the table can be sorted in either ascending or descending order of the highest or average scores.

This view will allow the user to manually indicate that any desired result shown in the last column of the table is related to the entry from the left column. That can be done by clicking the plus icon next to the corresponding result, in the right column. These relationships are registered in the database and will be the cornerstone for the Semantic Data Queries engine, described in the next chapter, to work.

5 Semantic Engine

The access to datasets is essential to feed the AI models that implement Policies. The number of datasets available and their completeness can contribute for a more accurate representation of the reality and therefore, a more accurate policy evaluation. To increase the number of datasets, a Dataset Discovery mechanism is required to aid the identification of the relevant sources of information available and make use of the datasets they provide. As different data source may be expressed using different data model and semantic concepts there is the need support the execution of semantic data queries.

The query of semantic data presents a challenge about how to integrate multiple data from multiple data sources when these data sources are described using different semantic models. This raises the problematics of how to discover data sources that match the requested criteria specified in the query, and then, how to get data from these data sources and how to aggregate data semantically annotated with a different model in single answer. Moreover, as the user/machine that made the query may only understand the semantic model used to describe the query, the results should be expressed in the same semantic model, independently of the semantic model originally used to describe them.

In this section is described the approach follow to tackle down this challenge, focusing on the identification of the representation of equivalent data concepts described on other semantic models, the required data conversions, and the collection of data from semantically heterogenous data sources.

5.1 Approach

The approach followed for reaching a solution to support the execution of semantic data queries starts with the usage of GraphQL⁴ to express desirable queries. GraphQL allows to express queries in an easy-to-understand approach by using a JSON-like language and a providing a broad ecosystem of tools that support the handling and execution of such queries. Moreover, GraphQL provides a flexible way to allow users to define queries and define the desirable structure of the query output.

After defining the GraphQL query for relevant datasets, it needs to be processed to support the collection of the datasets the meet the query conditions. In the figure bellow it is presented an overview of the Semantic Query System. The system presented corresponds to a customized setup, highly inspired in the typical architecture of a GraphQL system. However, to support the matching between different data models some changes needed to be made to the typical components and data flow and a new component needed to be added to take charge of identification of semantic mappings and corresponding data conversions.

Figure 17. Overview of the Semantic Query System

The system is composed by three main modules: Query Server, Semantic Matcher and Data Converter and Model Data Resolver. These modules are described below:

5.1.1 Query Server

This module is the responsible for receiving the query request and perform the first processing over it. It starts by identifying the Data Model that serves as context for the data requested. After that it performs the usual behaviour of a GraphQL server and analyses the query and extracts the

⁴ <https://graphql.org>

Measurable Quantities, i.e., types of data described in the specific Data Model. Alongside the Measurable Quantities, it is also extracted any filtering or constraint information that applies to the collection of data from that measurable content (e.g., locations, thresholds, etc.) and any operation that should be applied to that data sets collected (average of values, minimum value, maximum value, etc.).

This module is also responsible for the aggregation of the data of the query response according to the structure defined in the GraphQL query. Before providing it to the query requester, any operation requested in the query (such as averages, sum, etc.) is applied to the data.

5.1.2 Semantic Matcher and Data Converter

This module is responsible for performing the semantic matching between different data models and the execution of any data conversion required when matching data between different data models. When the Query Server analyses the GraphQL query, it extracts all the Measurable Quantities and any limitation that should be applied during the process of data discovery. After that the Semantic Matcher will receive the Measurable Quantities and discover their correspondence (if it exists) on other Data Models. This process is represented in Figure 18.

Figure 18. Semantic Match discover process

To support this matching, this module resorts to database with an index of semantic mappings that allows to identify all the known mappings between the pair (Data Model, Measurable Quantity). This database stores the results of the process described in Section 4 - Semantic Matchmaking. As a result, for a give pair of (Data Model, Measurable Quantity) extracted from the query, the indexer returns all semantic pairs with a known mapping semantic to the query pair.

As result of this matching, a query submitted to the Catalogue of Datasets and Policies that was initially restricted to data sources complying with a specific data model is translated to other data models enabling the gathering of data from a broader range of data sources. The filtering and constraint information must also be converted to the structure of the mapped data model to allow the usage of that information to limit the scope of data collection do be gathered from the data sources. This conversion may imply a simple change like the name of properties, or more complex transformations as the change of structures and units used to specify the restrictions.

When the identified information is extracted from the data sources, the results are sent back to Semantic Matcher and Data Converter to converted them according to the specification of Data Model of the original query. This conversion may imply the conversion of data units or more complex operation like changing the way the information is structured.

5.1.3 Model Data Resolver

After the generation of the different query equivalent representations on other data models, carried out by the Semantic Matcher and Data Converter, the original query and the equivalents must be executed, where the relevant information must be collected from data sources represented in each data model. The process of query execution is carried by a component called Model Data Resolver. This resolver implements the logic associated with the process of collecting data from a specific data source and presenting it on according to a specific Data Model.

To each Data Model can correspond multiple Model Data Resolvers and Data Source pairs. This information is recorded in an index, where for each Model all the available Data Resolvers and the Measurable Quantities that each Data Resolver can resolve are identified. To get the list of resolvers a query must be submitted to this Index where the pair (Model, Measurable Quantity) of interest is identified. This process is described in the figure bellow.

Figure 19. Detail of Data Resolver discovery process

Each data source will have its own Resolver. It holds information about how to access to the data source, implementing not only that way the information can be obtained (e.g., query in specific language, REST endpoint, etc.) but also any authentication mechanism (e.g., user/password mechanism, authentication token, certificates, etc.). As sometimes several data sources provide aggregations of data corresponding to multiple measurable quantities, it is also the responsibility of the Data Resolver the extraction of the information relevant for the initial query from the received data aggregation. The details of the operation of a Data Resolver are presented in the figure bellow.

Figure 20: Details of the Data Resolver operation

5.2 Implementation

This section describes how the implementation of the Semantic query works with a specific example. The flow starts with the input of a specific query. For this example, let us consider the query represented in Figure 21. In this query, the user requests values of Air Temperature and Relative Humidity according with the concepts defined in SemanticModel1 (a fictious Data Model used only for demonstration purpose).

```

{
  query {
    SemanticModel1 {
      Location {
        city (id: "Berlin")
        Country (id: "Germany")
      }
      Temperature {
        unit (id: Celsius)
      }
      Humidity
    }
  }
}
    
```

Figure 21. GraphQL example query

This query aims at collecting data in a specific location. Therefore, after defining the Semantic Data Model to be considered (identified with the SemanticModel1 object in the query), it is specified the target Location, by specifying the City and Country, as required by the SemanticModel1 Data Model. In this example the location chosen is Berlin in Germany. The next step consists in the identification of types of data that the user requires. As said before, the user is interested in Air Temperature and Relative Humidity that are represented in the query by Temperature and Humidity as it is the semantic correspondence in the selected Data Model (the SemanticModel1). Also, in the case of the Temperature, the user specifies that want to receive this information expressed in *Celsius* degrees.

The flow of processing and execution of this query is represented in Figure 22. It starts when the user sends the query to the Query Server. This server analyses the query splitting it into two atomic queries, one for each of the requested measures (Temperature and Humidity). This split is performed to provide more flexibility to the data discovering system as data can be retrieved from different data sources. In the each of this atomic query is also represent the restriction imposed in the original query, i.e., the location restriction, ensuring the only data on the specified location will be gathered, and information about the Data Model.

Figure 22. Example of a Semantic Query processing and execution

Each atomic query is then fed to the Semantic Matcher and Data Converter. This component looks to the indexes of semantic mappings, searching for equivalent definitions of the Measures specified in the atomic queries defined in other Data Models. In the example, a matching is found in the SemanticModel2. Temperature and Humidity in SemanticModel1 are mapped to Temp and AirHumidity in SemanticModel2. Since the atomic queries also presented restrictions regarding to the location of the information this restriction needs to also be mapped to the equivalent in the SemanticModel2. In this specific example, the Location(City, Country) in SemanticModel1 needs to be converted into the format Location(Coord X, Coord Y) in SemanticModel2. To be able perform this conversion, the Semantic Matcher needs not only to find the Semantic Matching in the Matching index but also retrieve and execute the set of rules needed to convert data between the two Location concepts. At the end of the execution of the Semantic Matcher and Data Converter we have both

the atomic queries generated by the Query Server and the equivalent atomic queries created from the semantic matchings found.

Having created the all the atomic queries, it is now the time to execute them. This execution is performed by the Model Data resolvers. For that, an index of resolvers is consulted to identify for each Data Model which Resolvers can provide data about the required measures. In this example 4 resolvers were identified, 2 for each Data Model. Each data resolver will connect to the associated data source and extract the request information from it, according to the logic implemented in the resolver. After acquiring all the relevant data, Data Resolver send that data to the Semantic Matcher and Data Converter, while keeping the context about the query that originated it. When receiving the data, the Semantic Matcher and Data Converter, identifies the data that are responses to the equivalent queries and converts them to the original Data Model – SemanticModel1. After ensuring that all the data is compliant with the right model, all the data responses are sent to the Query Server. This module, in its turn, aggregates all the received data and returns the response to the User.

6 Validation Data Models

In this section, 5 data models are presented with a summary description outlining their strengths, weakness, and applicability. These data models were selected based on their capability to represent a diverse range information. It is important to note, that these can often work together and complement each other. Rarely will there be a ready-made model that adequately fulfils all requirements or does everything well. These Data Models may be repurposed to suit specific needs, functioning at times as modules that can be coupled with each other to represent more complex data. Furthermore, these are not a complete listing of all existing data models but some that were chosen for internal testing of the Semantic Interoperability Toolkit.

6.1.1 Smart Data Models

The Smart Data Models [6] program is led by the FIWARE Foundation, TM Forum, OASC and IUDX. It aims to provide a wide range of data models for multiple domains. From Smart cities to Smart water and energy, having a common way to model the data from different domains helps ensure that there is a technical common ground, which then enables open innovation and procurement.

Users can submit new data models by following their schema template as in Figure 24. This allows for community creation of data models that become available to anyone who wishes to use or reuse them. They are publicly available in a GitHub repository⁵, and are contextualized within a domain (Smart Environment, Smart Energy...). Each domain then contains a list of entity types for which a data model exists (Figure 25).

While this schema provides a good modelling of the entity in relation to its properties, it does not adequately support the proper definition of said properties. Often, users want to describe a numeric attribute that is either a currency or a physical quantity, but the schema does not take this into consideration and as such, users insert the units they specifically use for their case in the description. This also results in discrepancies across data models where sometimes the unit is referred to being Celsius degrees, another time its degrees Celsius. This constitutes a good example of the problems to be addressed. In both instances, they refer to the same thing by different name. This is a normal drawback of user submitted forms but, one that can also be avoided by enforcing more strict rules on the property fields.

⁵ <https://github.com/smart-data-models>

Figure 23. Smart Data Models home page⁶

⁶ <https://smartdatamodels.org/>

```
// Instructions for creating your schema
// 1.- respect the HEADER
// 2.- there are 8 types of examples field1XXX to field9XXX
// HEADER ***Do not change any of these till next warning***
$schema = http://json-schema.org/schema
$schemaVersion = 0.0.1
$id = https://smart-data-models.github.io/XXXSubjectXXX/XXXDataModelXXX/schema.json
title = Smart Data models -XXXdataModelXXX schema"
modelTags = ""
description = description of a generic entity. You have to change this.
type = object
required[] = id, type
allof[0]
  $ref=https://smart-data-models.github.io/data-models/common-schema.json#/definitions/GSMA-Commons
allof[1]
  $ref=https://smart-data-models.github.io/data-models/common-schema.json#/definitions/Location-Commons
// HEADER ***this is the end of the header ***
// you can start configuring this
allof[2]
  properties

// Create a numeric attribute
field1XXX
  type = number
  minimum number = 0
  maximum number = 1
  description = Property. Model:'https://schema.org/Number'. Example of definition of a numerical attribute

// Create a simple string attribute
field2XXX
  type = string
  description = Property. Model:'https://schema.org/Text'. Example of definition of a numerical attribute

// Create a date time attribute
field3XXX
  type = string
  format = date-time
  description = Property. Model:'https://schema.org/Text'. Example of definition of a date-time attribute

// Create a relationship
relationship1XX
  anyOf[0]
    type = string
    minLength number = 1
```

Figure 24. Drafting a new data model⁷

.github/workflows	Create sync-2-upstream.yml	2 years ago
AeroAllergenObserved	corrected GeoProperty spelling	2 months ago
AirQualityForecast	corrected GeoProperty spelling	2 months ago
AirQualityMonitoring	updated AirQualityMonitoring/doc/spec.md	2 months ago
AirQualityObserved	corrected GeoProperty spelling	2 months ago
ElectroMagneticObserved	corrected GeoProperty spelling	2 months ago
EnvironmentObserved	corrected GeoProperty spelling	2 months ago
FloodMonitoring	corrected GeoProperty spelling	2 months ago
IndoorEnvironmentObserved	corrected GeoProperty spelling	2 months ago
MosquitoDensity	corrected GeoProperty spelling	2 months ago
NoiseLevelObserved	corrected GeoProperty spelling	2 months ago
NoisePollution	updated NoisePollution/doc/spec.md	2 months ago
NoisePollutionForecast	corrected GeoProperty spelling	2 months ago
PhreaticObserved	corrected GeoProperty spelling	2 months ago
RainFallRadarObserved	corrected GeoProperty spelling	2 months ago
TrafficEnvironmentImpact	corrected GeoProperty spelling	2 months ago
TrafficEnvironmentImpactForecast	corrected GeoProperty spelling	2 months ago
WaterObserved	corrected GeoProperty spelling	2 months ago

Figure 25. List of available entity types for Smart Environment⁸

⁷ <https://smartdatamodels.org/index.php/draft-a-data-model/>

⁸ <https://github.com/smart-data-models/SmartEnvironment>

6.1.2 UnitsNet

UnitsNet [7] provides a robust library with definitions for physical quantities and their units (Figure 26 and Figure 27). This data model does not immediately correlate to Smart Data Models but can complement existing works by ensuring the that said models correctly reference the unit or units that they use. Moreover, this library specifies conversions between units (for instance, from miles to meters or vice-versa). It also enumerates these within a given domain (Figure 28).

Acceleration.json	v5 Release (#982)	last month
AmountOfSubstance.json	v5 Release (#982)	last month
AmplitudeRatio.json	v5 Release (#982)	last month
Angle.json	v5 Release (#982)	last month
ApparentEnergy.json	v5 Release (#982)	last month
ApparentPower.json	v5 Release (#982)	last month
Area.json	v5 Release (#982)	last month
AreaDensity.json	v5 Release (#982)	last month
AreaMomentOfInertia.json	v5 Release (#982)	last month
BitRate.json	v5 Release (#982)	last month
BrakeSpecificFuelConsumption.json	v5 Release (#982)	last month
Capacitance.json	v5 Release (#982)	last month
CoefficientOfThermalExpansion.json	v5 Release (#982)	last month
Compressibility.json	🐛 Fix abbreviation for Compressibility.InverseMegapascal (#1099)	7 months ago
Density.json	v5 Release (#982)	last month
Duration.json	v5 Release (#982)	last month
DynamicViscosity.json	v5 Release (#982)	last month
ElectricAdmittance.json	v5 Release (#982)	last month
ElectricCharge.json	v5 Release (#982)	last month
ElectricChargeDensity.json	v5 Release (#982)	last month
ElectricConductance.json	v5 Release (#982)	last month
ElectricConductivity.json	v5 Release (#982)	last month
ElectricCurrent.json	v5 Release (#982)	last month
ElectricCurrentDensity.json	v5 Release (#982)	last month
ElectricCurrentGradient.json	v5 Release (#982)	last month

Figure 26. UnitsNet unit definitions⁹

⁹ <https://github.com/angularsen/UnitsNet/tree/master/Common/UnitDefinitions>

```

1  {
2  "Name": "Length",
3  "BaseUnit": "Meter",
4  "XmlDocSummary": "Many different units of length have been used around the world. The main units in modern use are U.S. customary units in the United States
and the Metric system elsewhere. British Imperial units are still used for some purposes in the United Kingdom and some other countries. The metric system is
sub-divided into SI and non-SI units.",
5  "BaseDimensions": {
6    "L": 1
7  },
8  "Units": [
9    {
10   "SingularName": "Meter",
11   "PluralName": "Meters",
12   "BaseUnits": {
13     "L": "Meter"
14   },
15   "FromUnitToBaseFunc": "{x}",
16   "FromBaseToUnitFunc": "{x}",
17   "Prefixes": [ "Nano", "Micro", "Milli", "Centi", "Deci", "Deca", "Hecto", "Kilo" ],
18   "Localization": [
19     {
20       "Culture": "en-US",
21       "Abbreviations": [ "m" ]
22     },
23     {
24       "Culture": "ru-RU",
25       "Abbreviations": [ "м" ]
26     },
27     {
28       "Culture": "zh-CN",
29       "Abbreviations": [ "米" ]
30     }
31   ]
32   },
33   {
34     "SingularName": "Mile",
35     "PluralName": "Miles",
36     "BaseUnits": {
37       "L": "Mile"
38     },
39     "FromUnitToBaseFunc": "{x} * 1609.34",
40     "FromBaseToUnitFunc": "{x} / 1609.34",
41     "Localization": [
42       {
43         "Culture": "en-US",
44         "Abbreviations": [ "mi" ]

```

Figure 27. Unit definition for length¹⁰

¹⁰ <https://github.com/angularsen/UnitsNet/blob/master/Common/UnitDefinitions/Length.json>

```

10 {
11   "Acceleration": {
12     "CentimeterPerSecondSquared": 1,
13     "DecimeterPerSecondSquared": 2,
14     "FootPerSecondSquared": 3,
15     "InchPerSecondSquared": 4,
16     "KilometerPerSecondSquared": 5,
17     "KnotPerHour": 6,
18     "KnotPerMinute": 7,
19     "KnotPerSecond": 8,
20     "MeterPerSecondSquared": 9,
21     "MicrometerPerSecondSquared": 10,
22     "MillimeterPerSecondSquared": 11,
23     "MillistandardGravity": 12,
24     "NanometerPerSecondSquared": 13,
25     "StandardGravity": 14
26   },
27   "AmountOfSubstance": {
28     "Centimole": 1,
29     "CentipoundMole": 2,
30     "Decimole": 3,
31     "DecipoundMole": 4,
32     "Kilomole": 5,
33     "KilopoundMole": 6,
34     "Megamole": 7,
35     "Micromole": 8,
36     "MicropoundMole": 9,
37     "Millimole": 10,
38     "MillipoundMole": 11,
39     "Mole": 12,
40     "Nanomole": 13,
41     "NanopoundMole": 14,
42     "PoundMole": 15
43   },
44   "AmplitudeRatio": {
45     "DecibelMicrovolt": 1,
46     "DecibelMillivolt": 2,
47     "DecibelUnloaded": 3,
48     "DecibelVolt": 4
49   },
50   "Angle": {
51     "Arcminute": 1,
52     "Arcsecond": 2,
53     "Centiradian": 3,
54     "Deciradian": 4,

```

Figure 28. Enumerated unit values¹¹

6.1.3 Semantic Sensor Network Ontology

The Semantic Sensor Network Ontology is a W3C Recommendation [8] which includes two main specifications: the SSN (Semantic Sensor Network) and SOSA (Sensor, Observation, Sample and Actuator). SOSA is the core of SSN and its main aim is to provide support for a wider audience and areas of application that use Semantic Web ontologies, while also being a minimal interoperability fall-back.

¹¹ <https://github.com/angularsen/UnitsNet/blob/master/Common/UnitEnumValues.g.json>

Figure 29. The SOSA and SSN ontologies and their vertical and horizontal modules¹²

An example of its use is found in Figure 30 where the ontology is used to record the observations made by a seismographer. The schemas for each prefix are identified at the top and then the ontology allows for a simple and readable specification of the main classes which, in the example case, are the earth, the sensor and the features of interest. The observation records who made it, what was the feature of interest and the property it recorded. The result also includes the unit in which the sensor recorded the value thanks to the QUDT schema [9].

The SSN ontology thus provides a robust and complete description of datasets capturing essential information of who recorded what, in what units, to which platform does the sensor belong and supports additional information such as location, the time of the recording, the observed phenomenon and the entity which originate. While this is specifically for sensors, it also includes a set of specifications for actuators and sampling.

¹² <https://www.w3.org/TR/2017/REC-vocab-ssn-20171019/>

EXAMPLE 14

```

@prefix rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#> .
@prefix rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>.
@prefix sosa: <http://www.w3.org/ns/sosa/> .
@prefix ssn: <http://www.w3.org/ns/ssn/> .
@prefix geo: <http://www.w3.org/2003/01/geo/wgs84_pos#> .
@prefix xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#> .
@prefix qudt-1-1: <http://qudt.org/1.1/schema/qudt#> .
@prefix qudt-unit-1-1: <http://qudt.org/1.1/vocab/unit#> .
@base <http://example.org/data/> .

# Observation #358 of seismograph VCAB DP1 BP 40 (Vineyard Canyon, Parkfield, Ca) measure
# a earth displacement speed of 0.000500 cm/sec at 8:23 am on April 18, 2017, Pacific
# Daylight Time.

<earth> rdf:type sosa:FeatureOfInterest ;
rdfs:label "earth"@en .

<VCAB-DP1-BP-40> rdf:type sosa:Sensor ;
rdfs:label "seismograph VCAB DP1 BP 40 (Vineyard Canyon, Parkfield, Ca)"@en ;
rdfs:seeAlso <https://earthquake.usgs.gov/monitoring/seismograms/153> ;
sosa:observes <VCAB-DP1-BP-40#groundDisplacementSpeed> .

<VCAB-DP1-BP-40#location> rdf:type sosa:FeatureOfInterest ;
rdfs:label "location of VCAB-DP1-BP-40"@en ;
geo:lat 35.8648067 ;
geo:long -120.6195831 ;
geo:alt 12.75 ;
sosa:isSampleOf <earth> .

<VCAB-DP1-BP-40#groundDisplacementSpeed> rdf:type sosa:ObservableProperty , ssn:Property ;
rdfs:label "the ground displacement speed at location of VCAB-DP1-BP-40"@en ;
sosa:isObservedBy <VCAB-DP1-BP-40> .

<VCAB-DP1-BP-40?t=2017-04-18T08:23:00-07:00> rdf:type sosa:Observation ;
sosa:madeBySensor <VCAB-DP1-BP-40> ;
sosa:hasFeatureOfInterest <VCAB-DP1-BP-40#location> ;
sosa:observedProperty <VCAB-DP1-BP-40#groundDisplacementSpeed> ;
sosa:hasResult [
rdf:type qudt-1-1:QuantityValue ;
qudt-1-1:numericValue "5e-4"^^xsd:double ;
qudt-1-1:unit qudt-unit-1-1:CentimeterPerSecond ] ;
sosa:resultTime "2017-04-18T08:23:00-07:00"^^xsd:dateTimeStamp .

# using SSN one can explicitly state that <VCAB-DP1-BP-40#groundDisplacementSpeed> is the
<VCAB-DP1-BP-40#location> ssn:hasProperty <VCAB-DP1-BP-40#groundDisplacementSpeed> ;

```

Figure 30. SSN ontology use example¹³

6.1.4 QUDT

Originally developed for the NASA Exploration Initiatives Ontology Models (NexIOM) project as part of the Constellation Program Initiative at the ARC (AMEAS Research Center), QUDT is a public charity non-profit organization which makes ontologies, derived models and vocabularies [10]. QUDT is a collection of several ontologies which are linked to each other as shown Figure 31s. QUDT main utility is to provide unit and quantity definitions ensuring interoperability across domains and records. Thus, it is used in SSN and can also be applied to other data models where unit definitions are limited such as in the case of Smart Data Models complementing them. The use cases for QUDT are unit conversion between single and complex types, dimensional analysis of equations, finding equivalent units in different systems of units and finding equivalent quantity kinds in different systems of quantities.

¹³ <https://www.w3.org/TR/2017/REC-vocab-ssn-20171019/#seismograph>

Figure 31. QUDT ontology¹⁴

6.1.5 SAREF

The Smart Applications Reference (SAREF) ontology specifies common concepts in smart applications, the relationships between them and the axioms to constrain the usage of the described concepts and relationships. It provides a set of building blocks that can be added or removed, according to the identified requirements, leading to an ontology that is reconfigurable. It follows four core concepts [11].

1. Reusability of concepts and relationships
2. Modularity of the ontology, allowing for its reconfiguration according to specific needs
3. Extensibility, accommodating for the future growth of the ontology
4. Maintainability, facilitating error detection and correction, new requirement accommodation and changes in the ontology

Figure 32. SAREF ontology¹⁵

¹⁴ <https://qudt.org>

¹⁵ <https://saref.etsi.org>

SAREF fulfils a similar role to SSN, putting the focus on the device (sensor or actuator) and allowing for the recording of measurements, which in SSN's case are observations. Contrary to SSN though, it provides built-in support for unit definitions and relates them to a `UnitOfMeasure` type. For instance, a `saref:TemperatureSensor` has a `saref:makesMeasurement` field that points to a `saref:Measurement` that then points to a `saref:UnitOfMeasure`. In this example, it would be temperature, but SAREF supports currency, energy, illuminance, power, pressure, and temperature unit types. It also uses W3 schemas for these units, as shown in Figure 33. These units are imports from the QU ontology resulting from the work done by the SysML 1.2 QUDV group [12].

Akin to SSN, SAREF allows the definition of the device but, it goes beyond the simple sensor-actuator model. A device can be an actuator, an appliance, HVAC, a meter or a sensor. Natively, it allows for the definitions of the class property as energy, humidity, light, motion, occupancy, power, pressure, price, smoke and temperature.

SAREF also possesses a list of extensions for several domains which includes energy, environment, water, eHealth, Smart Cities and many more (for a complete listing of all extensions visit: <https://saref.etsi.org/extensions.html>).

```
{
  "@id" : "saref:TemperatureUnit",
  "@type" : [ "owl:Class", "rdfs:Resource" ],
  "localName" : "TemperatureUnit",
  "comment" : {
    "@language" : "en",
    "@value" : "The unit of measure for temperature"
  },
  "isDefinedBy" : "saref:v3.1.1/",
  "label" : {
    "@language" : "en",
    "@value" : "Temperature unit"
  },
  "subClassOf" : "saref:UnitOfMeasure",
  "@context" : {
    "label" : {
      "@id" : "http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#label"
    },
    "comment" : {
      "@id" : "http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#comment"
    },
    "subClassOf" : {
      "@id" : "http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#subClassOf",
      "@type" : "@id"
    },
    "isDefinedBy" : {
      "@id" : "http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#isDefinedBy",
      "@type" : "@id"
    },
    "localName" : {
      "@id" : "http://example.org/localName"
    },
    "@vocab" : "https://saref.etsi.org/core/",
    "owl" : "http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#",
    "rdf" : "http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#",
    "xml" : "http://www.w3.org/XML/1998/namespace",
    "saref" : "https://saref.etsi.org/core/",
    "xsd" : "http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#",
    "dcterms" : "http://purl.org/dc/terms/",
    "rdfs" : "http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#",
    "vann" : "http://purl.org/vocab/vann/",
    "foaf" : "http://xmlns.com/foaf/0.1/"
  }
}
```

Figure 33. TemperatureUnit definition

6.1.6 Analysis

The different data models possess differing qualities. While the Smart Data Models were created specifically for Smart contexts, it lacks flexibility for contexts which may have more unique needs. This is not the case for SSN. It is a much more flexible tool that can be applied to a variety of different scenarios. However, SSN may be more difficult to understand and use when compared to Smart Data Models.

UnitsNet does not capture this entity and properties dynamic, but it does provide a complete and actively maintained library of physical quantities and units fulfilling a similar role to QUDT. This is crucial to ensure interoperability because simply knowing a value from an observation is insufficient

information, one needs to know its unit and Smart Data Models does not possess sufficient specifications on this issue, thus, it can be used in a similar fashion as QUDT is used in SSN.

SAREF presents itself as a more complete and repurposable ontology for multiple domains. It already considers the question of unit types as opposed to Smart Data Models. When compared to the SSN, they are very similar being both modular, of a more general character and developed with a vision for use in “Smart” contexts.

As such, Smart Data Models presents itself as a ready-made solution for specific domains where someone as already developed a data model to use “out of the box”. SSN and SAREF represent ontologies of a more general character, enabling interoperability across domains but with the caveat of requiring more user knowledge for their use.

QUDT and UnitsNET can provide support for unit definitions in situations where the model does not provide them. Being narrower data models, the data is better described, and these be used as either an alternative or as an extension to other models.

Each model is thus unique which makes it a challenge to develop a general solution to import them to the web framework. A script such as the one shown in **Error! Reference source not found.** must be developed for each data model. There are also no hard requirements as to constitutes a Data Model, Data Concept, Measurable or Unit. The case of QUDT is the most straight forward because it is already structured in a similar way with Disciplines, quantity kinds and units (Figure 34).

Figure 34. QUDT GitHub Repository

A more complex case is that of the Smart Data Models (Figure 35). Our approach was to create a Smart Data Models Data Model for the framework which would contain i.e., be the parent of other Data Models such as Smart Cities, Smart Energy and so on. Inside these there are different folders containing the data structures for different entities, that we considered to be parent Data Concepts to the directories they further possess. Finally, within these directories, the JSON schema describing the data structure is found from where the Measurable quantities, which in this this instance are very often entity properties, are extracted along with the units (Figure 36).

The process does not follow strict guidelines but rather heuristics for the classification into the catalogue’s four hierarchy levels. Units are the lowest level entity and refer only to an actual value type that a measurable may take. Measurables may not have a Unit as in the case of some properties, or it may have a Unit which is Unitless or Dimensionless (QUDT supports this for example). A Measurable refer to JSON property fields or columns in a CSV, they are something that takes some value and describes some higher entity. A Data Concept is this higher entity, Weather for instance, in which Temperature is a measurable that partially describes it in some unit. Depending on the level of granularity desired, concepts can encapsulate other concepts for instance Weather

in Smart Data Models contains other elements such as Weather Observed and Weather Forecast where each has unique Measurables although they may also share some. QUDT as well, has disciplines which contain other Disciplines. Finally, these concepts are contained in a Data Model because they all share the same data structure i.e., the way that data is presented.

This heuristic approach provides flexibility to accommodate for the uniqueness of each model, but it does mean that different people can view them in different ways and thus classify them differently in the framework’s hierarchy.

Figure 35. Smart Data Models GitHub page

Figure 36. Measurables and Units for Smart Data Models Weather Observed Entity

7 Conclusions and Future Works

This document, D3.3 “Holistic Interoperability Toolkit V1” it’s the first version and reports the work performed within T3.2 “Ontologies and Archetypes for Semantic Interoperability”.

The fact that data can be presented in different ways proves to be a challenge when attempting to collect information from heterogenous sources. Our solution attempts to index a wide range of different data models and create a unifying representation that provide a common comparison base that supports the translation of semantic concepts of a model into the concepts other model through the semantic matchmaking solution.

The proposed matchmaking solution is based on vector search, i.e., the text embedding of the search query is matched against the previously calculated embeddings of the content to be searched and, using a search-powered engine, the most similar results are returned. As for the implementation itself, it relies on the *knn* operator from Elasticsearch, which operates upon fields of the *dense_vector* type, and whose content are 512-dimensional text embeddings obtained via TensorFlow's Universal Sentence Encoder. The results are then presented in a table, where buttons are provided for the user to register, in the database, the relationship between similar Data Concepts, Data Models, Measurable Quantities and Units.

The Semantic Engine serves to support users/machines in discovering and exploring datasets regardless of the semantic description used to describe to them. The presented system is inspired on the elements of a typical GraphQL backend architecture supported by the functionalities of a Semantic Catalogue of Data Models implemented using the Unparallel Innovation Web Framework. The 3 core modules of this system are described (Query Server, Semantic Matcher and Data Converter and Model Data Resolver), highlighting their behaviour, inputs and outputs, and interactions with the different indexes of the catalogue. An example is provided to demonstrate the behaviour of the Semantic Query System under a specific usage scenario.

The current version of the technologies presented in this document focuses on the handling the discovery and retrieving of datasets with disparate semantic descriptions. The next iteration of the deliverable, D3.4 "Holistic Interoperability Toolkit V2", will extend the support to the Public Policies, to facilitate the discover and reuse of existing Public Policies.

Five Data Models were used to validate the technologies of the Semantic Interoperability Toolkit. Those Data Models were chosen based on their relevance in the Data Model representation in general and capability to represent datasets from different domains. The next steps will be on the validation of the technologies using the Data Models used by the AI4PublicPolicy pilots.

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